

Heritage Buildings and Objects' Digitisation & Visualisation within the Cloud

Pioneering Advanced Digital Heritage Solutions

HERITALISE transforms cultural heritage (CH) documentation and preservation through advanced digitization and AI tools, revealing both visible and hidden CH features.

Key Highlights:

- **State-of-the-Art Digitization:** Captures CH assets in unmatched detail.
- **AI-Driven Post-Processing:** Optimizes data integration with machine learning.
- **Knowledge Graph Environment:** A dynamic platform for exploring CH objects and insights.
- **Web-Based Ecosystem:** Supports the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH).

HERITALISE empowers professionals with cutting-edge tools and data for CH documentation, preservation, and exploration.

The Pillars

The Impacts

Our Demo Sites

West Highland Museum, Fort William, Scotland

Partners: WHM, USTAN

Building type: Category B listed

Potential outreach: 90,000 in person visitors per year, 200 heritage practitioners

Use Case:
Transforming Heritage through Digital Innovation

- Digitizing the Jacobite & Carmichael Collections
- Enhanced Digital Exhibits
- Immersive VR Experiences

Timespan Museum, Highlands, Scotland

Partners: HHAS, USTAN

Building type: Museum and landscape

Potential outreach: Small museum and art gallery with international standing

Use case:
Immersive Heritage Experiences

- VR Room
- Testbed for visualizing artifacts
- Kildonan Landscape
- VR models showcasing Scotland's trade legacy and the 19th-century herring boom.
- Community Engagement through virtual events

Reggia di Venaria Reale, Turin, Italy

Partners: CCRS, CCR, POLITO

Building type: UNESCO site

Potential outreach: strong outreach potential by serving as a testing ground for new digital technologies in CH audience engagement

Use case:
Advanced Digital Preservation

- Building Digitization
- Architectural Analysis
- Landscape Heritage
- Object Documentation through 3D imaging and tomography

Villa Portelli, Kalkara, Malta

Partners: HM

Building type: Historic villa

Potential outreach: 300,000 visitors per year; tens of international stakeholders, restorers, companies

Use case:
Innovating Heritage Through Digital Storytelling and Preservation

- Oral History Digitisation
- Building Digitisation
- Methodology Testing employing LIDAR, photogrammetry, laser scanning, and RTI
- Public Outreach utilizing VR/AR, holograms, and projections

Meet HERITALISE – Bridging Heritage and Innovation for a Deeper Cultural Connection

<https://heritalise-ecch.eu/>

